

Multiple Solutions for Type II Cell Death Research

CD BioSciences, a US-based CRO serving the global life science research community, has recently launched a suite of research solutions to support scientists in the study of cell death, specifically the type II cell death, including Regulator Identification, Phenotype Analysis, and Chemical Screening.

In multicellular organisms, cell death is a critical and active process for maintaining tissue homeostasis and eliminating potentially harmful cells. There are three major morphologically distinct types of cell death, i.e., apoptosis (type I cell death), autophagic cell death (type II), and necrosis (type III). All three types can be executed by different and sometimes overlapping signaling pathways that respond to specific stimuli.

Autophagic cell death (ACD), also known as type II cell death, is defined morphologically (especially by transmission electron microscopy) as a type of cell death that occurs in the absence of chromatin condensation but is accompanied by massive autophagic vacuolization of the cytoplasm. Although the term ACD is a linguistic invitation to assume that cell death is carried out by autophagy, this term only describes cell death with autophagy.

ACD has been implicated in physiological and pathological events. Although substantial evidence suggests that the inhibition of apoptosis is critical for tumorigenesis, elimination of cancer cells may also be mediated by ACD, and there is evidence that decreased autophagic activity is associated with tumorigenesis. In addition, some recent findings indicate that autophagy plays a dual role in cancer, acting in an environmentally dependent manner.

As a trusted CRO, CD BioSciences now offers global clients a variety of solutions covering all aspects of life science research, including autophagic cell death, ranging from Regulator Characterization, Regulator Identification, Phenotype Analysis, Chemical Screening to Cell Death Characterization.

Examples

Regulator Characterization studies the molecular function of certain regulators in cell death signaling pathways.

Regulator Identification identifies gene regulators participating in certain cell death signaling pathways.

Phenotype Analysis analyzes cellular phenotypes regulated by the gene/protein of interest.

Chemical Screening screens inhibitors or activators of certain types of cell death.

Cell Death Characterization identifies and characterizes the types of cell death under specific conditions.

CD Biosciences is committed to meeting all the needs of researchers in signaling pathway research and will support customers' innovative discoveries by providing high quality reagents and comprehensive solutions. For customers interested in more information on cell death solutions or other signaling pathways, please visit CD BioSciences at <https://www.cd-biosciences.com/>.

About CD BioSciences

CD BioSciences is a trusted research product supplier and CRO based in New York. With high-quality reagents and comprehensive services, CD BioSciences is a one-stop shop devoted to advancing signaling pathway studies for researchers. The company is committed to fulfilling all demands in the research of signaling pathways and provides high-quality reagents and comprehensive solutions to support innovative discoveries.